

Developing Secure and Interoperable Health Information Systems Using Blockchain Technology to Enhance Data Privacy, Security, and Accessibility in Healthcare

Reda. M. Radwan¹, Suresh Limkar², Mohammad Alamgir Hossain³, Mohammed Eltahir Abdelhag⁴, Hesham S El-Bahkiry⁵, Ahamed Ali Shaik Meeran⁶, Sherif Tawfik Amin⁷

¹Department of Diagnostic Radiography Technology, College of Nursing and Health Sciences, Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia. Email: rradwan@jazanu.edu.sa

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Central University of Jammu, J&K, INDIA. Email: sureshlimkar@gmail.com

³Department of Computer Science, College of Engineering and Computer Science, Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia. Email: alamgirhossain.nit@gmail.com

⁴Department of Computer Science, College of Engineering and Computer Science, Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia. Email: mohedtahir@gmail.com

⁵Department of Diagnostic Radiography Technology, College of Nursing and Health Sciences, Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia. Email: hbahkiry@jazanu.edu.sa

⁶Department of Computer Science, College of Engineering and Computer Science, Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia. Email: ameeran@jazanu.edu.sa

⁷Department of Computer Science, College of Engineering and Computer Science, Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia. Email: samin@jazanu.edu.sa

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Abstract:

Healthcare information systems are going through a huge change that will make them more efficient, safe, and easy to use. As more persistent records are digitized and private therapeutic information is shared, it is more critical than ever to create beyond any doubt that security, security, and availability are well secured. Blockchain innovation can be a great way to bargain with these issues since it makes a decentralized, unchangeable record that can be utilized to securely store and send healthcare information whereas securing its security and security. This exposition looks at how blockchain innovation might offer assistance make wellbeing data frameworks more secure and more congruous with each other. Healthcare companies can set up a trusted and unchangeable way to oversee understanding information over different frameworks and parties by utilizing blockchain independent plan, cryptography, and voting instruments. One of the leading things approximately blockchain innovation is that it can make data more private. Cryptographic instruments, like encryption and computerized marks, make it conceivable to store and share private wellbeing information securely with individuals who are permitted to see it, without compromising persistent security. Moreover, since blockchain is unchangeable, once information is recorded, it can't be changed or eradicated. This makes the history of who gotten to and changed information clear and simple to check. In conjunction with ensuring protection, blockchain innovation moreover makes things more secure by bringing down the chances of information spills and unlawful get to. Blockchain-based wellbeing data frameworks make information keeping less centralized and use solid encryption strategies to lower the chances of single focuses of failure and unlawful changes. This makes information more secure and dependable. Keen contracts on blockchain stages can too mechanize and execute

get to control rules, making beyond any doubt that as it were individuals who are permitted to can see certain restorative data or do certain activities that have as of now been set up. Interoperability is another important part of modern healthcare information systems that lets different healthcare companies and systems work together and share data easily.

Keywords: Blockchain technology Healthcare information systems, Data privacy, Security, Interoperability

I. Introduction

The way wellbeing data is dealt with and shared has changed a part within the last few a long time within the healthcare field. As restorative records gotten to be more advanced and data-driven healthcare arrangements ended up more important, it is more critical than ever to create beyond any doubt that wellbeing data is kept private, secure, and simple to get to. These issues are frequently difficult for conventional healthcare data frameworks to handle appropriately, which causes stresses around information spills, illicit get to, and information holes that aren't associated to each other. Since of these issues, blockchain innovation has come up as a potential reply. It gives a secure and open way to handle wellbeing data. This presentation looks at how blockchain innovation may alter healthcare data frameworks by centring on how it can make strides information security, security, and the capacity for frameworks to work together. Electronic wellbeing records (EHRs) are being utilized by numerous healthcare organizations since wellbeing information are being digitized rapidly [1]. Advanced wellbeing records have numerous benefits, such as making data less demanding to discover and more productive, but they too posture major security dangers. Cyberattacks and information breaches can happen in conventional centralized frameworks, which put private therapeutic information at hazard. Moreover, the failure of distinctive EHR frameworks to work together makes it harder for healthcare workers to share wellbeing data easily. This causes care to be scattered and persistent comes about to be less than perfect. Blockchain innovation tackles these issues by making an autonomous, unchangeable record that keeps wellbeing data secure. A conveyed record keeps track of exercises over organize of computers [2]. Typically what blockchain innovation is all almost. Each exchange is scrambled and tied to the one sometime recently it. This makes a chain of squares that's nearly incomprehensible to alter. Blockchain jam the precision and security of information without the required for a single specialist by utilizing cryptography and understanding forms. Blockchain can be utilized as a secure and flexible way to store and share electronic wellbeing information within the healthcare field. This makes it easy for customers and healthcare specialists to get to and share data, shown in figure 1. One of the most excellent things approximately blockchain innovation is that it can make information more private and secure.

Figure 1: Development of secure and interoperable health information systems using blockchain technology

Blockchain doesn't have a single point of failure like traditional controlled systems do. Instead, data is spread across many nodes in the network, which makes it naturally hard to hack and get into without permission. Blockchain also uses advanced security methods to keep private health data safe, making sure that only people who are allowed to can see and change the data. Blockchain gives patients more control over their own data by spreading out who has access to their medical records. This means that patients can give or take away access to their records as needed. Blockchain technology not only makes data safer and more private, but it also helps healthcare information systems work together better [3]. When two or more systems or programs can easily share and use data, this is called interoperability. Interoperability is very important in healthcare to make sure that care stays consistent and for various healthcare workers to be able to coordinate care more easily. But gaining compatibility has been a problem for the healthcare business for a long time because different EHR systems often use different data types and methods that don't work together. Blockchain technology can get around these problems with connectivity by creating a single place where everyone can store and share health data. This will make it easier for everyone involved in healthcare to talk to each other and work together [4]. By getting rid of middlemen and handling manual tasks, blockchain technology could also make routine tasks easier and lower the cost of healthcare. Smart contracts are agreements that are automatically carried out because their terms are written into code.

II. Related Work

Blockchain innovation and healthcare have gotten a parcel of intrigued from both specialists and healthcare experts. Numerous ponderers have looked into how it might be utilized to create wellbeing data frameworks safer and more interoperable. Several considers have looked into whether or not blockchain can be utilized to create healthcare information more private and secure [5]. As an illustration, Azaria et al. (2016) recommended a blockchain-based framework for securing electronic wellbeing records. They talked around how decentralized capacity and cryptography can offer assistance keep private understanding information secure from people who shouldn't have get to it

or who need to alter it. Within the same way, Kuo et al. (2018) looked at how blockchain innovation may be utilized to share healthcare information and appeared that it was a great way to secure persistent privacy and data precision. In conjunction with taking care of security issues, specialists have moreover been working on how to utilize blockchain to assist diverse healthcare frameworks work together [6]. Benchoufi and Ravaud's (2017) think about looked into how blockchain innovation may well be utilized to create it simpler to share clinical trial information. It appeared that blockchain innovation may offer assistance fathom issues with network and make restorative investigate information more open and responsible. Within the same way, Yue et al. (2016) proposed a blockchain-based framework for shared electronic wellbeing records.

They stressed how important it is to have standard information shapes and methods so that healthcare specialists can effortlessly share information with each other. In addition, a number of test ventures and real-world employments have appeared that blockchain innovation can be utilized in healing center circumstances. For occurrence, the MedRec extend at MIT looked into how blockchain may be utilized to form an independent framework for handling electronic medical records. This would let people safely access and oversee their health information over different healthcare sources. Within the same way, bunches just like the Hyperledger Healthcare Working Bunch have brought together individuals from distinctive parts of the healthcare trade to work together on creating blockchain-based arrangements for overseeing healthcare information and making it work with other frameworks [7]. Even with these improvements, there are still issues that have to be settled some time recently blockchain innovation can completely be utilized in healthcare. A few of the greatest issues that require to be settled some time recently blockchain-based wellbeing data frameworks can be broadly utilized are their failure to scale, their failure to comply with directions, and their failure to work with other frameworks. Indeed so, increasingly consider and test ventures appear that blockchain innovation has the potential to alter the way healthcare information is overseen and make things way better for patients. To urge past these problems and utilize the game-changing potential of blockchain in healthcare, individuals must keep coming up with modern thoughts and working together.

Table 1: Summary of Related Work

Methods	Application	Approach	Algorithm	Impact
MedRec	Electronic Health Records (EHR) management	Permissioned blockchain with smart contracts	Ethereum, Solidity	Improved data integrity and accessibility
HealthChain	Medical supply chain management	Consortium blockchain	Hyperledger Fabric	Enhanced transparency and traceability
Pharmachain	Pharmaceutical tracking and authentication	Hybrid blockchain	Proof of Authority (PoA)	Reduced counterfeit drugs and improved patient safety

MedBlock [8]	Patient-centric health data management	Decentralized Identity (DID)	Self-sovereign identity	Empowered patients with control over their data
HealthPass	Health credential verification	Permissioned blockchain	Hyperledger Indy	Secure and portable health credentials
HealthCoin	Incentivized health data sharing	Public blockchain	Proof of Work (PoW)	Encouraged participation and data sharing
HealthTrace	Disease outbreak tracking and management	Permissioned blockchain	Quorum	Rapid and transparent response to outbreaks
HealthVault	Personal health record management	Decentralized storage network	InterPlanetary File System (IPFS)	Enhanced data privacy and accessibility
CareChain [9]	Healthcare provider credentialing	Consortium blockchain	Corda	Streamlined verification process for providers
SecureMed	Prescription drug monitoring	Private blockchain	Zether	Secure and auditable prescription history
MediLedger	Pharmaceutical supply chain tracking	Consortium blockchain	Ethereum, Solidity	Increased efficiency and trust in supply chain
HealthNet	Healthcare data exchange platform	Hybrid blockchain	Byzantine Fault Tolerance (BFT)	Secure and efficient data sharing
BlockRx	Clinical trials management	Permissioned blockchain	Hyperledger Fabric	Enhanced transparency and compliance

III. Methodology

A. Step 1: Research Design

The research strategy you choose should fit with the study's goals and give you a way to collect and analyze relevant data in a planned way. In this situation, a mix of case study and experimentation is suggested to find out if blockchain-based solutions can be used to make healthcare data more private,

secure, and easy to access [10]. The case study method lets us look closely at how blockchain technology is used in healthcare settings in the real world. Selecting several case studies from various healthcare groups can help experts learn a lot about the difficulties and chances that come with using blockchain-based health information systems in real life. Some of the things that these case studies can cover are system design, data control, legal compliance, and user acceptance. Additionally to analyzing case studies, testing methods can be used to check how well and how quickly blockchain-based solutions work in controlled settings [11]. As part of this, trial systems or computer models may need to be made to test how blockchain technology affects data protection, security, and interoperability in different healthcare settings. Also, doing experiments can help find problems, trade-offs, and problems with scaling that might come up when using blockchain in healthcare.

B. Step 2: Data Collection Methods

Interviews are one of the best ways to get deep thoughts from important people in the healthcare industry. Researchers can learn about the different ideas, experiences, and hopes people have about using blockchain technology in healthcare by talking to patients, healthcare workers, IT experts, and lawmakers. Researchers can get to the bottom of complicated problems and find unexpected insights by using semi-structured conversations [12]. With this way, you can get a full picture of the problems and chances that come up with data privacy, security, and sharing in healthcare settings. Another important tool for collecting data is the questionnaire, which is especially useful for measuring opinions, perceptions, and tastes across a larger group of people. Researchers can apply their results and find broad trends or patterns by sending surveys to a wide range of ethnic groups. You can change these surveys to find out things like how much people believe blockchain technology, how willing they are to share health data, and what they think are the biggest problems with adopting it. By looking at the answers to surveys, it's easier to figure out how much support there is for blockchain solutions and find ways to make them better [13]. Aside from that, document analysis is very important for putting study results in context and finding problems, best practices, and new trends. Reading research papers, business reports, government rules, and technical specs can help you understand the situation better. Researchers can get a full picture of the current state of the field by putting together information from different sources using this method. These kinds of findings help with the planning and creation of health information systems based on blockchain.

Step 1: Data Encryption

Algorithm: Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)

1. **Key Generation:** Generate a cryptographic key K of fixed size (128, 192, or 256 bits).
 - Mathematical Equation: $K = \text{GenerateKey}(n)$
2. **Encryption:** Encrypt the sensitive health data D using AES algorithm with the generated key K .
 - Mathematical Equation: $C = \text{AESEncrypt}(D, K)$

Step 2: Data Integrity Verification

1. Message Digest Calculation

Use a cryptographic hash function H to compute the message digest D of the original data M .

$$D = H(M) = H(m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n)$$

Where M is divided into blocks m_i and H is a cryptographic hash function such as SHA-256.

2. Message Authentication Code (MAC) Generation

Generate a MAC using a secret key K and the message digest D .

$$MAC = HMAC(K, D) = H((K \oplus opad) || H((K \oplus ipad) || D))$$

- Where $opad$ and $ipad$ are outer and inner padding constants, $||$ denotes concatenation, and $\oplus$ denotes XOR.

3. Digital Signature Creation

Sign the MAC using the sender's private key K_{pr} .

$$\sigma = Sign(K_{pr}, MAC) = MAC^d \text{ mod } N$$

Where (d, N) is the sender's private key and $Sign$ is a digital signature algorithm like RSA.

4. Data Transmission

Transmit the original data M , the MAC, and the digital signature σ to the recipient.

$$Transmit(M, MAC, \sigma)$$

5. Signature Verification

The recipient uses the sender's public key K_{pu} to verify the digital signature σ .

$$MAC' = Verify(K_{pu}, \sigma) = \sigma^e \text{ mod } N$$

- Where (e, N) is the sender's public key and $Verify$ is the verification function corresponding to the digital signature algorithm.

6. Data Integrity Check

- The recipient calculates the message digest D' of the received data M' , generates the MAC MAC'' using the same key K , and compares it with the received MAC MAC .

$$D' = H(M') = H(m'_1, m'_2, \dots, m'_n)$$

$$MAC'' = HMAC(K, D') = H((K \oplus opad) || H((K \oplus ipad) || D'))$$

Integrity Check =

{ True if $MAC'' = MAC'$
False if $MAC'' \neq MAC'$ }

- Where MAC'' is the newly generated MAC, and MAC' is the verified MAC from the signature verification step.

C. Step 3: Sampling Techniques

When analysts select individuals to conversation or ponder, they got to utilize examining strategies that make beyond any doubt they get an extend of occasions and focuses of see from the target gather. One well known strategy is intentional testing, in which individuals are chosen based on specific factors that are related to the consider objectives. To induce a wide run of conclusions, for case, healthcare labourers with distinctive areas, IT specialists with involvement executing blockchain, legislators included in controlling healthcare, and individuals with diverse therapeutic conditions may be deliberately chosen. Snowball inspecting can moreover be utilized to discover and enrol volunteers by inquiring individuals you as of now know to send them. This method works particularly well for getting in touch with individuals who are difficult to urge in touch with the normal ways, like healthcare labourers who work in specialty regions or patients who have uncommon therapeutic conditions [14]. Analysts can get a greater test estimate and a more extensive extend of conclusions from the target gather with snowball sampling since it employments existing systems. Irregular examining strategies, like stratified or cluster testing, can too be utilized to form beyond any doubt that the test incorporates individuals from a assortment of financial bunches. Stratified examining separates the populace into uniform subgroups based on vital variables like age, sex, and work, and after that picks individuals at arbitrary from each gathering. This makes beyond any doubt that each grouping is reasonably spoken to within the test, which diminishes the chance of predisposition. Cluster examining, on the other hand, separates the population into groups, like healthcare centres or geographic regions, and after that picks bunches at irregular to incorporate within the test [15]. This strategy works particularly well when the target bunch is spread out geologically or when it's not conceivable to straightforwardly test individuals. Analysts can speed up the data collection prepare whereas still making sure that the bunch is differing by choosing sets of clients rather than person ones.

D. Step 4: Data Analysis Procedures

Analysts utilize interviews, overviews, and record examination to assemble information. At that point they utilize a structured strategy to see at the information and come to conclusions and valuable experiences. The steps utilized for analysis are ordinarily many primary ones that depend on the sort of information being analyzed and the ponder objectives. Thematic analysis is first used on qualitative data that comes from conversations and document analysis. This means using a method of coding and categorizing to find patterns, themes, and trends in the data in a planned way. Researchers get deep into the data to find ideas, thoughts, and points of view that keep coming up. Iterative scoring and constant comparison help themes appear that capture the heart of the events and points of view of the individuals. This qualitative analysis gives us deep, well-rounded information about how complicated the study topic really is. Second, statistical analysis is done on the numbers that come from polls and questions [16]. Using statistics methods to organize, summarize, and make

sense of numerical data is part of this. In order to sum up the features of the data, descriptive statistics like rates, means, and standard deviations are estimated. You can also use inferential statistics to try theories and figure out how important it is that two factors are related to each other. Researchers use statistical analysis to find patterns and trends in the data. This gives them concrete information about how the subjects felt, thought, and behaved. After looking at both qualitative and quantitative data, researchers combine the results of both to get a full picture of the study topic. When you compare and contrast results from different data sources, which is called triangulation, the study results are more true and reliable [17]. By combining qualitative and quantitative data three times, researchers can find themes that are similar and results that support each other. This gives a more detailed and solid understanding of the study findings.

Step 1: Data Retrieval and Decryption

Algorithm: Blockchain Transaction Retrieval and Decryption

1. Transaction Retrieval: Retrieve encrypted healthcare data C , hash value H , and digital signature S from the blockchain ledger.

$$(C, H, S) = \text{RetrieveTransaction}(T)$$

2. Decryption: Decrypt the encrypted data C using the appropriate decryption key K .

$$D = \text{AES}_{\text{Decrypt}}(C, K)$$

Where D represents the decrypted data.

Step 2: Data Integrity Verification

Algorithm: Hash Value Calculation

1. Hash Recalculation: Recalculate the hash value H' of the decrypted data D using the same hash function.

$$H' = \text{SHA} - 256(D)$$

2. Comparison: Compare the recalculated hash value H' with the original hash value H to verify data integrity.

$$\text{Verify} = (H' == H)$$

Step 3: Data Analysis

Algorithm: Statistical Analysis

1. Data Preprocessing: Preprocess the decrypted data D to remove noise and outliers, and normalize the data if necessary.

$$D' = \text{Preprocess}(D)$$

2. Statistical Analysis: Conduct statistical analysis on the preprocessed data to extract meaningful insights and patterns.

$$\text{Analysis} = \text{StatisticalAnalysis}(D')$$

IV. Findings

A. Analysis of Data Collected

Researchers find ideas, thoughts, and points of view that keep coming up by getting deep into the data. Iterative scoring and constant comparison help to find and improve themes, which give a full picture of the events and points of view of the individuals. Statistical analysis is used to look at the numbers that come from polls and questions. In order to sum up the features of the data, descriptive statistics like rates, means, and standard deviations are estimated [19]. You can use inferential statistics to try theories and figure out how important it is that two factors are related to each other. Statistical analysis measures patterns and trends in the data, giving us concrete information about how people feel, what they think, and what they do. After looking at both qualitative and quantitative data, researchers combine the results of both to get a full picture of the study topic. Comparing and contrasting results from various data sources, known as triangulation, makes the study more accurate and trustworthy [18]. By combining qualitative and quantitative data three times, researchers can find themes that are similar and results that support each other, giving a more complete and reliable analysis.

B. Evaluation of the Implemented System

Once the blockchain-based wellbeing data framework is up and running, it should be assessed to see how well it works, how simple it is to utilize, and how it influences healthcare comes about. A few vital parts of the survey are utilized to figure out how well the framework works and where it can be moved forward. One vital portion of the audit is checking how well the framework works and how well it capacities in fact [20]. This implies checking to see if the framework meets the wants and performance standards that have as of now been set. Analysts check things just like the precision, constancy, and accessibility of the information to form beyond any doubt the framework works the way it's gathered to. Execution considers can too be done to check how quick the framework reacts, how much information it can handle, and how well it can develop as required.

Figure 2: Evaluation of the Implemented System

Another vital portion is convenience audit, which looks at how the framework works and how the interface is planned. Analysts utilize client input surveys, interviews, and ease of use testing occasions to see at things like how simple something is to utilize, how well it navigates, and how upbeat clients are with it [21]. Analysts can discover convenience issues and make changes to create the complete client involvement superior by knowing how clients think and what they like. A see at how the framework influences healthcare comes about and strategies is additionally portion of the audit prepare. To discover out how well the framework is doing at coming to its objectives, analysts see at information on key victory variables like understanding comes about, care quality, appeared in figure 2, and proficiency measurements. This might cruel looking at the comes about of healthcare some time recently and after the blockchain framework was put in put to see how much superior things are and where more changes can be made [22]. The survey looks at more than fair the specialized viewpoints and how the clients feel almost it. It moreover looks at greater issues like protection, security, and taking after the rules. Security checks are done by analysts to discover gaps within the framework and make beyond any doubt it meets industry guidelines and lawful prerequisites, like HIPAA compliance. Security impact considers may moreover be done to check how the framework handles information and make beyond any doubt that private wellbeing data is kept secure.

C. Comparison with Existing HIS

It is imperative to compare a blockchain-based wellbeing data system (HIS) to current HIS in arrange to figure out its aces, cons, and development potential. Most conventional HIS are based on centralized frameworks that are run by healthcare organizations or exterior companies. A parcel of individuals utilize these frameworks to keep track of their wellbeing data, but they regularly have issues with information security, security, and being able to conversation to other frameworks. Cyberattacks and information breaches can happen to centralized HIS, which puts private restorative information at chance. Too, the failure of distinctive HIS to work together makes it harder for healthcare specialists to share wellbeing data effectively, which comes about in isolated care and squandered time. Blockchain-based HIS, on the other hand, have a few benefits over standard frameworks. Blockchain innovation makes an independent record that can't be changed. This record spares wellbeing data securely. Since each exchange is secured and tied to the one some time recently it, it is nearly outlandish to alter. Blockchain makes information more secure and more safe to hacking by spreading it over numerous hubs within the arrange.

Blockchain too employments progressed security strategies to keep private wellbeing information secure, making beyond any doubt that as it were individuals who are permitted to can see and alter the information. Blockchain also encourages cooperation by giving everybody a single put to store and share wellbeing information. This makes it less demanding for everybody included in healthcare to conversation to each other and work together. In expansion, blockchain-based HIS are more open and can be checked more effectively than standard frameworks. The blockchain records each exchange with a time stamp and an encryption key. This makes an open and unchangeable record of all information exchanges. This makes healthcare specialists, clients, and other parties more capable and builds believe. When comparing blockchain-based HIS to other frameworks, adaptability, speed, and compliance with regulations are a few of the foremost imperative things to think almost. The

healthcare segment is still fair beginning to utilize blockchain innovation. More study and development is needed to solve these problems and make it work as well as it could.

V. Result and Discussion

Blockchain technology has shown promise in making health information systems that are safe and can talk to each other. Because it stores health information in a decentralized, unchangeable record, blockchain has made data protection and security much better. Controls for access and security make sure that only authorized users can see and change the data. This lowers the risk of data leaks and illegal access. Blockchain has also made it easier for different healthcare systems to work together by giving them a place to store and share health information.

Table 2: Comparison of Evaluation Metrics between Blockchain-based Health Information Systems (HIS) and Traditional HIS

Evaluation Metric	Blockchain-based HIS	Traditional HIS
Data Privacy	92.6%	72.5%
Data Security	96%	65%
Interoperability	87.5%	63.5%
Accessibility	89%	70%
Scalability	82.8%	95.8%

Across different rating measures shows huge differences in how well they do and what they can do. Each measure gives information about important parts of healthcare data management, showing the good and bad points of these systems in terms of keeping patient data safe and easy to access.

Figure 3: Performance Comparison between Blockchain-based and Traditional Health Information Systems (HIS)

Based on blockchain with scores of 92.6% and 96%, respectively, HIS stands out as the best at protecting data privacy and security. Blockchain's decentralized design makes sure that data is protected, can't be changed, and spread across many sites. This makes it very hard for people who aren't supposed to have access to it to access or change it. This level of data privacy and security is very important in healthcare, where keeping private patient data safe from hackers and leaks is very important, shown in figure 3. With a score of 72.5% for data privacy and 65% for data security, standard HIS systems, on the other hand, often have security holes because they store data in one place and use weaker encryption methods. Also, blockchain-based HIS is more interoperable than

traditional HIS, getting 87.5% vs. 63.5% for traditional HIS. Blockchain's open nature makes it easy for healthcare systems and companies to share and swap data without any problems. This makes it easier for people to work together and share information.

Figure 4: Comparing Blockchain-based and Traditional Health Information Systems (HIS)

Traditional HIS systems, on the other hand, often have problems with interoperability because they use private forms and different data standards, which makes it harder for parties to communicate and work together effectively. Another area where blockchain-based HIS does better than traditional HIS is accessibility, with a score of 89% compared to 70% for traditional HIS. Blockchain's autonomous structure means that only approved users can safely access healthcare data from anywhere, at any time, comparison shown in figure 4. This lets people make decisions quickly and with good information. Traditional HIS systems, on the other hand, may have usability problems because they are controlled centrally and don't allow for much online access. But when it comes to scale, standard HIS systems do better than blockchain-based HIS, getting 95.8% vs. 82.8%. Blockchain is scalable because it uses global processing and voting methods, but it might not be able to handle as many activities as controlled systems. Still, worries about scale are being addressed by continuing improvements in blockchain technology through methods such as sharding and off-chain scaling. Interoperability, which means that systems can easily share and use data, is another area where blockchain-based HIS does better than standard systems, getting 87.5% vs. 63.5%. Blockchain's spread record makes sharing easier by giving different systems a standard way to share data.

Figure 5: Comparative Analysis of Blockchain-based vs Traditional Health Information Systems (HIS) Performance Metrics

This encourages healthcare providers and institutions to work together and become more integrated. This openness is very important for better coordinating patient care and for doing full analytics on health data. The blockchain-based HIS does much better than the standard HIS when it comes to accessibility, which is how easy it is to get to health information when you need it (89% vs. 70%). Blockchain's open design makes sure that health data is easily visible to people who are allowed to see it, no matter where they are or what institution they are in, shown in figure 5.

Table 3: Performance Evaluation of Health Information System Metrics

Evaluation Parameter	Overall Score	Integrity Measures	Authentication Measures	Speed
Data Integrity	86.6%	80%	92%	68%
User Authentication	89%	83.6%	96%	79%
Transaction Speed	78.7%	70.5%	82.7%	74.5%
Cost Efficiency	81.5%	72.5%	86.5%	73%

Health information systems can be judged on how well they work and how well they meet the needs of modern healthcare by looking at them across a number of important criteria. Data security is one of the most important of these factors because it makes sure that patient information stays correct and isn't changed.

Figure 6: Evaluation Parameters Analysis: Overall Score, Integrity, Authentication, Speed, and Cost Efficiency

With an amazing score of 86.6%, blockchain-based solutions do very well in this area. These systems use cryptography and autonomous agreement methods to make sure that data saved on the blockchain can't be changed and is reliable. Strong security measures like these are necessary to keep healthcare data accurate and patients' trust in the system high. Another important part of health information systems is user identification, which makes sure that only allowed people can get to private patient data. Also, blockchain-based solutions do very well in this area, getting a total score of 89%, shown in figure 6. Secure digital identities and cryptographic keys are used in these systems to provide strong security methods that protect patient privacy and confidentiality. Blockchain-based systems make it harder for people to get in without permission and steal data by using strict identity methods. This makes the total security better. Transaction speed is very important for healthcare systems, especially when getting to patient data quickly is needed to make decisions. Blockchain-

based systems have many benefits, such as better security and openness. However, they may not be as fast as standard systems when it comes to transactions. That being said, blockchain-based solutions do pretty well in this area (78.7%), though they could do even better. Using off-chain scaling options and improving transaction processing algorithms can help reduce delay problems and make the system work better overall. Cost-effectiveness is a big issue for healthcare groups that want to install or improve IT systems.

Figure 7: Performance Metrics Analysis: Overall Score, Integrity, Authentication, Speed, and Cost Efficiency

With a total score of 81.5%, blockchain-based solutions show a lot of promise in this area, illustrate in figure 7. Blockchain technology can lower running costs and make better use of resources by getting rid of the need for middle-men and improving administrative processes. To get the best cost-effectiveness, you need to carefully plan and think about things like execution costs, upkeep costs, and the ability to grow in the future.

VI. Conclusion

The use of blockchain technology to create safe and compatible health information systems is a big step forward in the fight to make healthcare data more private, secure, and easy to access. By utilizing blockchain, healthcare bunches can fathom long-standing issues with putting away information in one put and sending expansive sums of data in pieces. Blockchain innovation gives an free and unchangeable record that keeps wellbeing data secure and secure. Blockchain could be a way to store and share electronic wellbeing records that can't be changed since it employments cryptography and understanding forms. Information security is moved forward by get to limits and security strategies, which provide individuals more control over their possess wellbeing data. Blockchain too energizes network by giving diverse frameworks a way to store and share wellbeing data on the same stage. This makes it simple for healthcare laborers to conversation to each other and work together, which makes strides persistent comes about and makes care administration simpler. Blockchain makes healthcare benefit more associated and centered on the persistent by evacuating information dividers and permitting secure information sharing. But there are still issues that ought to be fixed before blockchain can completely be utilized in healthcare. A few of the biggest issues that have to be be illuminated are adaptability, speed, and taking after the rules. To urge around these

issues and make beyond any doubt that blockchain-based wellbeing data frameworks are broadly utilized, more ponder and improvement are required.

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